

Primer Dismenoreli Üniversite Öğrencilerinde Fiziksel Aktivite, Kinezyofobi, Anksiyete Ve Depresyon İlişkisi: Covid-19 İzolasyon Döneminden Bulgular

Relationship Between Physical Activity, Kinesiophobia, Anxiety And Depression In University Students With Primary Dysmenorrhea: Findings From The Covid-19 Isolation Period

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Öz

Amaç: Bu çalışmanın amacı, sosyal izolasyon döneminde primer dismenore yaşayan üniversite öğrencilerinde fiziksel aktivite, kinezyofobi, anksiyete ve depresyon düzeylerini araştırmak ve bu değişkenler arasındaki ilişkiyi incelemektir.

Yöntem: Bu kesitsel, online anket çalışmasına İstanbul Üniversitesi Cerrahpaşa Sağlık Bilimleri Fakültesi'nden 272 kadın öğrenci çalışmaya katıldı. Değerlendirmeler arasında Görsel Analog Skalası, Menstrüel Belirti Ölçeği, Uluslararası Fiziksel Aktivite Anketi, Tampa Kinezyofobi Skalası, Durum-Kişilik Kaygı Envanteri ve Beck Depresyon Envanteri yer aldı. Veriler COVID-19 sosyal izolasyon dönemi sırasında toplandı ve Spearman korelasyonu ile analiz edildi.

Sonuçlar: Öğrencilerin %50,2'si şiddetli primer dismenore bildirdi. Menstrüel semptomlar, ağrı ile orta düzeyde pozitif korelasyon gösterirken ($r = 0,639$, $p < 0,01$), kişilik kaygısı ($r = 0,191$, $p < 0,05$) ve depresyon ($r = 0,276$, $p < 0,01$) ile zayıf pozitif korelasyonlar gösterdi. Kinezyofobi, fiziksel aktivite ($r = -0,137$, $p < 0,05$) ve durum kaygısı ($r = -0,179$, $p < 0,01$) ile negatif, depresyon ile ise pozitif korelasyon ($r = 0,285$, $p < 0,01$) gösterdi.

Tartışma: Sosyal izolasyon döneminin öğrencileri hem fiziksel aktivite yönünden hem de psikolojik iyilik hali yönünden etkilediği görülmektedir. Fiziksel aktivite düzeyi ile kinezyofobi arasında bir ilişki bulunmaktadır. Diğer yandan psikolojik parametrelerdeki etkilenim fiziksel parametreleri de etkilemiş olabilir. Egzersiz tabanlı müdahalelerin uygulanması fiziksel aktivite ve kinezyofobiyi iyileştirirken psikolojik parametrelere de katkıda bulunabilir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: COVID 19, Fiziksel Aktivite, Kinezyofobi, Primer Dismenore.

Abstract

Purpose: The aim of this study was to investigate the levels of physical activity, kinesiophobia, anxiety, and depression among university students experiencing primary dysmenorrhea during the period of social isolation and to examine the relationships among these variables.

Methods: 272 female students from Istanbul University's Faculty of Health Sciences participated in this cross-sectional, online survey study. Assessments included the Visual Analogue Scale, Menstrual Symptom Scale, International Physical Activity Questionnaire, Tampa Scale for Kinesiophobia, State-Trait Anxiety Inventory, and Beck Depression Inventory. Data were collected during the COVID-19 social isolation period. Data were analyzed using Spearman's correlation.

Results: Overall, 50.2% of students reported severe primary dysmenorrhea. Menstrual symptoms showed a moderate positive correlation with pain ($r=0.639$, $p<0.01$), and weak positive correlations with trait anxiety ($r=0.191$, $p<0.05$) and depression ($r=0.276$, $p<0.01$). Kinesiophobia negatively correlated with physical activity ($r=-0.137$, $p<0.05$) and state anxiety ($r=-0.179$, $p<0.01$), and positively with depression ($r=0.285$, $p<0.01$).

Conclusion: The period of social isolation appears to have affected students both in terms of physical activity and psychological well-being. A relationship was observed between physical activity level and kinesiophobia. On the other hand, the impact on psychological parameters may also have influenced physical parameters. Implementing exercise-based interventions may improve physical activity and kinesiophobia while also contributing to psychological parameters.

Key Words: COVID 19, Kinesiophobia, Physical Activity, Primary Dysmenorrhea.

1. Introduction

Primary dysmenorrhea (PD) is a gynecological condition characterized by pain and spasms, particularly in the lower abdominal region, occurring before or during menstruation in the absence of any underlying pelvic pathology (1). Its global prevalence varies widely, ranging from 16.8% to 81% (2). PD has been associated with several factors, including early menarche, low body mass index, high menstrual blood flow volume, depression and anxiety, and smoking (3). Moreover, PD has been linked to reduced quality of life, increased absenteeism from work or school, decreased participation in sports and social activities (4), and a higher prevalence of sleep disturbances (5).

Physical activity is defined as any bodily movement that increases energy expenditure and enhances physical fitness (6). It is known to reduce stress, produce antinociceptive effects, and decrease prostaglandin F_{2α} levels—factors closely linked to the pathophysiology of PD (7). Accordingly, regular exercise is strongly recommended as a management strategy for PD, supported by high-level evidence (8). Meta-analyses have reported moderate-quality evidence for the effectiveness of physical activity and therapeutic exercise in reducing pain intensity, low-quality evidence for decreasing pain duration, and very low-quality evidence regarding improvements in quality of life (7,9). Among university students, significant improvements in pain intensity and duration have been observed following eight weeks of aerobic exercise and yoga (10). A term related to physical activity, kinesiophobia is a fear-avoidance behavior that arises from anxiety about re-experiencing pain or injury during movement (11). Although it is frequently studied in relation to chronic pain conditions such as low back pain, neck pain, or following anterior cruciate ligament surgery (12), it is also thought to occur in cases of abdominal, back, and thigh pain associated with PD (13). Moreover, a correlation has been reported between high pain intensity and fear of movement in individuals with PD (13). It is plausible that physically inactive individuals with a sedentary lifestyle may be more prone to developing kinesiophobia.

This study was planned during the COVID-19 pandemic, a period when individuals were required to stay at home and universities continued education

through online platforms. During this time, mandatory social isolation among students led to a decline in physical activity levels (14). In addition, as another consequence of social isolation, increased levels of anxiety and depression were reported during the period when this study was planned (15), and evidence on this issue has continued to accumulate in subsequent years (16). It is considered that reduced physical activity may exacerbate the severity of dysmenorrhea and kinesiophobia and may be associated with increased levels of anxiety and depression.

Accordingly, the aim of this study was to investigate the levels of physical activity, kinesiophobia, anxiety, and depression among university students experiencing PD during the period of social isolation and to examine the relationships among these variables.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Participants

This cross-sectional correlational study was conducted between March and June 2021 using an online survey administered to female students from the Faculty of Health Sciences at Istanbul University. The study period coincided with an extended stay-at-home phase due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The inclusion criteria were: being a female student over the age of 18 enrolled in the Faculty of Health Sciences at Istanbul University, and experiencing pain before or during menstruation with a regular menstrual cycle (28 ± 7 days). Exclusion criteria included the presence of digestive or urinary tract disorders, gynecological or immune system diseases, psychiatric conditions, chronic pain syndromes, a history of childbirth, current pregnancy, use of intrauterine devices or oral contraceptives, previous pelvic surgery, or a diagnosis of secondary dysmenorrhea. The study population consisted of female students in the Faculty of Health Sciences ($n = 1100$). The required sample size was calculated using the Raosoft Sample Size Calculator (<http://www.raosoft.com/samplesize.html>). Based on a PD prevalence of 72% among university students (17), with a 5% margin of error and 95% confidence interval, the minimum sample size was determined to be 242.

2.2 Ethical Considerations

The study was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki. Ethical approval was obtained from the Istanbul University

Non-Interventional Clinical Research Ethics Committee (IRB: 2021/12). Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their involvement in the study.

2.3 Data Collection Tools

Data were collected using an online survey platform (Google Forms). Female students from the Faculty of Health Sciences were invited to participate via their university email addresses and the student information system. Those who accepted the invitation and met the inclusion and exclusion criteria were included in the study.

The questionnaire was divided into two sections. The first section contained the research invitation, informed consent form, and screening questions for inclusion and exclusion criteria. Participants who met the criteria were asked to provide informed consent. Only those who approved the consent form proceeded to the second section, which included the outcome measures. Participants who did not provide consent were excluded from the study.

The Participant Assessment Form collected data on physical characteristics (age, height, weight, smoking and alcohol use, chronic illnesses) and dysmenorrhea-related features, including age at menarche, duration and frequency of menstruation, pain intensity and onset time, and use of analgesics.

Visual Analog Scale (VAS): Pain intensity during dysmenorrhea was assessed using the VAS (0-10) (18).

Menstrual Symptom Scale (MSS): The physical, psychological, and social effects of menstrual symptoms were assessed using the MSS. It consists of 22 items rated on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (never) to 5 (always). Total scores range from 22 to 110, with higher scores indicating more severe symptoms. The total MSS has high reliability, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.92 and a test-retest correlation coefficient of 0.89 ($p < 0.001$) (19).

International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ): This questionnaire assessed participants' physical activities of varying intensities and sedentary time. It records the duration and frequency of walking, moderate, and vigorous activities, combined to calculate a total MET-minute score. Based on this score, participants were classified as inactive (<600 MET-min/week), low active (600–3000 MET-min/week), or sufficiently active (>3000 MET-min/week). Turkish versions of the IPAQ short form is reliable and valid in assessment of physical activity (20).

Tampa Scale for Kinesiophobia (TSK): The 17-item TSK assesses fear of movement and re-injury, fear-avoidance. Scores range up to 68, with higher scores

indicating greater fear-avoidance behavior. The test-retest reliability is 0.806 (95% CI=0.720-0.867) (21).

State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI): The STAI was developed to measure state anxiety and trait anxiety. The scale consists of a total of 40 items, with 20 items measuring state anxiety (STAI I) and 20 items measuring trait anxiety (STAI II), utilizing a four-point Likert-type scale (22).

Beck Depression Inventory (BDI): The scale assesses depression severity using 21 items scored on a 0–3 Likert scale, yielding total scores from 0 to 63. Higher scores indicate more severe depressive symptoms. It has acceptable reliability and validity (23).

2.4 Data Analysis

The statistical analysis was performed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences software (SPSS version 21.0). The normality of data distributions was assessed using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, which indicated that most variables did not follow a normal distribution. Consequently, the Spearman Correlation Test, a non-parametric method appropriate for non-normally distributed data, was used to evaluate the relationships between symptoms. In all analyses, a p -value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

3. Results

Of the 277 volunteers, 5 were excluded due to missing data, resulting in a final sample of 272 participants. The mean age of the participants was 21.55 ± 3.31 years, and the mean body mass index (BMI) was 21.31 ± 3.16 kg/m². Regarding the severity of primary dysmenorrhea (PD), 14% of participants reported mild symptoms, 35.8% moderate, and 50.2% severe. The general characteristics of the participants are summarized in Table 1.

The mean total Menstrual Symptom Scale (MSS) score was 108.65 ± 23.70 . Among the participants, 20.5% reported frequent use of painkillers, while 12.8% reported consistent use. Detailed information related to menstruation and pain is presented in Table 2.

The Spearman correlation test was used for the correlation analysis of the outcome measures, with r and p values presented in Table 3. According to this analysis, the MSS showed a moderate positive correlation with the VAS ($r = 0.639$; $p < 0.01$), a low positive correlation with the STAI II ($r = 0.191$; $p < 0.05$), and a low positive correlation with the BDI ($r = 0.276$; $p < 0.01$). The TSK demonstrated a low negative correlation with the IPAQ ($r = -0.137$; $p < 0.05$) and the

STAI I ($r = -0.179$; $p < 0.01$), and a low positive correlation with the BDI ($r = 0.285$; $p < 0.01$). A low positive correlation was also found between the STAI I and STAI II ($r = 0.260$; $p < 0.01$). Additionally, the BDI showed a low positive correlation with the VAS ($r = 0.146$; $p < 0.05$) and the STAI II ($r = 0.259$; $p < 0.01$).

4. Discussion

This study aimed to investigate the levels of physical activity, kinesiophobia, anxiety, and depression among university students experiencing PD during the period of social isolation and to examine the relationships among these variables. As expected, a relationship was found between physical activity and kinesiophobia; however, no association was observed between pain and kinesiophobia. Moreover, anxiety and depression were associated with both menstrual symptoms and kinesiophobia.

Low physical activity levels are considered a risk factor that can increase pain severity in PD (24). While one study has reported that physical activity decreases as pain intensity increases (25), the other has found similar activity levels across groups with varying pain intensities (26). When comparing our physical activity levels (mean IPAQ value) with those reported in previous studies, our findings were higher than in one study (25) and lower than in another (26). A study that compared the physical activity levels of the same students before and during the pandemic reported a decline during the pandemic period (27), and the physical activity level observed in our study is consistent with the pre-pandemic data of that study.

Table 1. Participant general information

	Yes n (%)	No n (%)
Do you have a chronic illness?	33 (12.1)	239 (87.9)
Do you take any medication regularly?	45 (16.5)	227 (83.5)
Do you smoke?	44 (16.2)	228 (83.8)
Do you drink alcohol?	62 (22.8)	210 (77.2)

Table 2. Information about menstruation and pain

Menstrual parameters	Value
Age of first menstruation (year) X±SD	13.00± 1.35
Average period duration (day) X±SD	5.88± 1.43
Menstrual pain onset time n(%) menstruation begins	After 18 (6.6) 115 (42.1) 140 (51.3)
With menstruation	Before menstruation
Menstrual Symptom Scale Scores:	Negative affect/somatic complaint 42.6 ± 9.73 Pain 58.72± 12.53 Coping 8.79± 2.43 Total score 108.65± 23.70
Do you use painkillers to control your menstrual pain? n (%)	Never 59 (21.6) Rarely 123 (45.1) Frequently 56 (20.5) Always 35 (12.8)

Abbreviations: X±SD: Mean and Standard Deviation values

Therefore, our results can be considered approximately average relative to the overall pre-pandemic literature. It is important to note that data collection took place during a prolonged stay-at-home period due to the COVID-19 pandemic. This period was characterized by reduced social interaction, increased anxiety, and widespread physical inactivity. These factors may have contributed to the overall low physical activity levels observed in this study and should be taken into consideration when interpreting the findings.

Kinesiophobia has been extensively studied in conditions such as knee and low back pain, where higher levels of kinesiophobia have been associated with increased pain severity. In a study conducted among university students with PD, a positive correlation was found between kinesiophobia and pain; individuals with higher levels of kinesiophobia reported more severe pain and lower exercise participation (13). Similarly, a study involving female athletes reported that most participants experienced menstrual pain and developed kinesiophobia and fear-avoidance behaviors (28). In the present study, kinesiophobia levels were found to increase as physical activity levels decreased; however, no significant association was observed between pain severity and kinesiophobia.

Table 3. Results of Spearman correlation analysis

		VAS	MSS	TSK	STAI I	STAI II	BDI	X±SD
IPAQ	r	.012	.099	-.137*	.097	-.031	.095	1276.76±1626.23
	p	.849	.103	.024	.109	.610	.119	
VAS	r		.639**	.047	-.108	.084	.146*	6.15±2.33
	p		.000	.436	.075	.169	.016	
MSS	r			.102	-.059	.191**	.276**	108.66 ±23.7
	p			.093	.334	.002	.000	
TSK	r				-.179**	.069	.285**	35.44±6.64
	p				.003	.255	.000	
STAI I	r					.260**	-.209	40.71±6.38
	p					.000	.001	
STAI II	r						.259**	47.81±7.32
	p						.000	
BDI								16.86±8.2

Abbreviations: VAS: Visual Analog Scale, MSS: Menstruation Symptom Scale, TSK: Tampa Scale for Kinesiophobia, STAI: State-Trait Anxiety Inventory, BDI: Beck Depression Inventory, X±SD: Mean and Standard Deviation values, IPAQ: International Physical Activity Questionnaire, r, Spearman Rho, p: Sig. (2-tailed), *: Correlation significant at 0.05 level, **: Correlation significant at 0.01 level

The level of kinesiophobia observed in our study was consistent with the data of the group described as “sometimes experiencing pain during the menstrual period” in the related study (28); this finding may be due to the fact that all pain levels in our study were analyzed together without subgroup classification. On the other hand, one possible reason for the lack of an association between pain severity and kinesiophobia could be the presence of additional fears related to the pandemic period, such as restrictions on going outside and fear of contracting the illness.

In a study of university students, 34.1% reported engaging in exercise to cope with dysmenorrhea (29), and in another study among young women reported that 22% performed diaphragmatic breathing exercises and 23% engaged in aerobic exercise (13). The therapeutic effect of physical activity on PD symptoms is well-documented, and regular exercise is recommended for women with PD. It has been suggested that exercise may elevate the pain threshold by regulating blood steroid hormone levels and increasing endorphin release, thereby reducing dysmenorrhea and its associated symptoms (30). In particular, aerobic and

stretching exercises have been shown to alleviate symptom severity (31), while practices such as Pilates and yoga also hold potential benefits for women with PD (30). Walking program performed three days for 8-week was shown to reduce both pain intensity and fear of movement (32), emphasizing the importance of physical activity in managing PD.

About the psychological conditions, the literature reports that psychological conditions such as anxiety and emotional sensitivity frequently accompany PD. High levels of anxiety and depression have been reported in adolescents with dysmenorrhea (33). The importance of assessing mental health and providing appropriate psychological support for individuals with PD is emphasized (34). One of the findings of this study as well was the association between trait anxiety and menstrual symptoms, as well as between state anxiety and kinesiophobia. Depression was found to be correlated with pain, menstrual symptoms, kinesiophobia, and anxiety. Both the chronic and acute pain associated with PD can lead to alterations in the nervous system, particularly in pain perception pathways. While pain negatively impacts mental health,

compromised mental health, in turn, influences how pain is perceived. In this context, differing from previous studies, the elevated anxiety and depression associated with social isolation during the pandemic period in which our study was conducted may have exerted a more pronounced influence on the manifestation of menstrual symptoms and pain.

This study was conducted during a period of remote education due to the COVID-19 pandemic, during which participants were required to stay at home for extended periods. This created a natural inactivity condition- an effect that would be difficult or unethical to replicate under normal circumstances. The results of our study provide data related to the COVID-19 isolation period, which can be compared in future research. The consequences of this sedentary period were reflected in the participants' pain and physical activity scores. Our findings also offer data for developing physical activity programs or mental health support strategies for students.

A limitation of the study was the absence of a healthy control group for comparison, which necessitated the interpretation of findings in the context of existing literature. Nevertheless, the study contributes valuable insight into the effects of the pandemic period on physical activity and pain in individuals with primary dysmenorrhea. Furthermore, to the best of the authors' knowledge, this is the first study to investigate the relationship between physical activity and kinesiophobia in university students with dysmenorrhea, representing a key strength of the research.

As a result of this study, it was observed that physical activity is associated with kinesiophobia in university students with dysmenorrhea, and that a sedentary lifestyle may increase the likelihood of experiencing dysmenorrhea-related kinesiophobia. The impact of social isolation on students' psychological well-being, which may have contributed to an increase in pain and menstrual symptoms, is a concern that requires attention and intervention. Exercise-based interventions that encourage physical activity may help enhance psychological well-being and prevent or reduce kinesiophobia. Future research should include kinesiophobia as an outcome measure to evaluate the effects of different exercise modalities or physical activity programs. In this way, the cycle of inactivity, pain, fear of movement, and further inactivity may be interrupted.

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